

MARESEC 2021

European Workshop on *Maritime Systems Resilience and Security*

The first **European Workshop on Maritime Systems Resilience and Security** (MARESEC) was dedicated to the research on Resilience, Security, Technology and related Ethical, Legal, and Social Aspects (ELSA) in the context of Maritime Systems, including but not restricted to (Offshore/Onshore) Infrastructures, Navigation and Shipping and Autonomous Systems.

The event, which was organized by the Institute for the Protection of Maritime Infrastructures of the German Aerospace Center (DLR), occurred virtually on June, 14th 2021 and counted on 86 participants. Out of all submitted extended abstracts, 26 submissions had been selected for presentation. Additionally, 3 works of undergraduate and graduate students have been presented (the final schedule can be found in the appendix). The authors are affiliated to institutions from Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Norway, Portugal, South Korea, Spain and United Kingdom.

From the **submitted full papers**, 14 works have been selected for publication. These works are as follows:

Tino Flenker and Jannis Stoppe

MARLIN: An IoT Sensor Network for Improving Maritime Situational Awareness

Aman Kumar and Jaya Shradha Fowdur

A Framework for Extended Multisensor Multitarget Tracking with Vessel Size Categorization

Colin von Negenborn

One Ocean, One Heritage? A New Foundation of Ecocentrism in Marine Environmental Ethics

Irene López García, Alberto Gallego Rapado, Manuel Plaza Jiménez and Ignacio Isabel González

Situational Awareness for Maritime Surveillance

Bruno Arich-Gerz and Nicola Wendt

Resilience, Acceptability and the Postcolonial Moment – Towards a Culture-Sensitive Approach to Security Research in Maritime Contexts

Sarah Barnes, Maurice Stephan, Frank Sill Torres, Alexander Gabriel, Arto Niemi, Carl Wrede and Nicola Wendt

The COSMICS (Container Scanning by Muon-based Imaging using Cosmic rayS) project; introduction, preliminary results and concepts.

Leonard Günzel

Robotic Infrared Vision: Enabling operation in fog and low-light environments

Yasin Alhamwy, Simon Watson, Joaquin Carrasco, Glen Cooper and Kurt Geihs
A Feasibility Analysis of Tether Localisation for Mobile Robots

Peter Danielis, Mostafa Assem Mohamed Ali and Helge Parzyjegl

Modeling Underwater Communication for Autonomous Underwater Vehicles in OMNeT++

Bernhard J. Berger, Christian Maeder and Salva Daneshgadeh Çakmakçı

Threat Modeling Knowledge for the Maritime Community

Karin Bernsmed, Per Håkon Meland, Ravi Borgaonkar, Guillaume Bour and Egil Wille

Security challenges in multi-modal communication

Jorg Brauchle, Ralf Berger, Tina Hiebert and Daniel Hein

Towards optical maritime surveillance with high-altitude platforms

Marc Asendorf, Hasanur Jaman Seam, Christian Maeder, Salva Daneshgadeh Çakmakçı and Bernhard J. Berger

Where are my containers?

Jennifer Mielniczek, Corinna Köpke, Kushal Srivastava and Egon Schröder

Cyber-Physical Security and Resilience for Offshore Wind Farms

The following table lists all **reviewers**:

Name	Affiliation	Country
Alexander Gabriel	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Arto Niemi	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Bartosz Skobiej	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Carl Wrede	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Daniel Lichte	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Daniel Hein	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
David Heuskin	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Davies William de Lima Monteiro	Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG)	BRA
Dennis-Kenji Kipker	University of Bremen	GER
Dieter Kraus	Bremen University of Applied Sciences	GER
Enno Peters	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Evelin Engler	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Frank Fiedrich	University of Wuppertal	GER
Izabela Kotowska	Maritime University of Szczecin	POL
James Imber	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Jussi Aaltonen	Tampere University	FIN
Kari Koskinen	Tampere University	FIN
Karsten Sohr	Uni Bremen	GER
Matthias Vahl	Fraunhofer	GER
Maurice Stephan	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Michael Ehrhardt	Fraunhofer	GER
Michael Stadermann	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER

Nikolai Kulev	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Peter Danielis	University of Rostock	GER
Ralf Berger	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Rikke Bjerg	University of London	UK
Sandeep Kumar	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Sarah Barnes	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Sergey Voinov	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	GER
Stanislaw Iwan	Maritime University of Szczecin	POL
Stefanie Schubert-Polzin	Magdeburg-Stendal University of Applied Sciences	GER
Sylvia Bach	University of Wuppertal	GER
Tobias Meisen	University of Wuppertal	GER

In the name of the whole organizing team we thank all authors and reviewers for their effort and the technical team for their valuable support.

Frank **Sill Torres** and Edgardo **Solano Carrillo**
Workshop General Co-chairs

Schedule of the 1st European Workshop on Maritime Systems Resilience and Security (MARESEC 2021)

Session A1 - Situation Awareness

Session Chair Jannis Stoppe

ID	Start	Title	Authors
A1-1	09:10	EO-ALERT: A Satellite Architecture for Autonomous Maritime Monitoring in Almost-Real-Time	Murray Kerr, Stefania Cornara, Stefania Tonetti, Stefan Wiehle, Otto Koudelka, Enrico Magli, Riccardo Freddi, Silvia Fraile and Cecilia Marcos
A1-2	09:30	Situational Awareness for Maritime Surveillance	Irene López García, Alberto Gallego Rapado, Manuel Plaza Jiménez and Ignacio Isabel González
A1-3	09:50	MARLIN: An IoT Sensor Network for Improving Maritime Situational Awareness	Tino Flenker and Jannis Stoppe
A1-4	10:10	Towards optical maritime surveillance with high-altitude platforms	Jorg Brauchle, Ralf Berger, Tina Hiebert and Daniel Hein

Session B1 - Resilience

Session Chair Frank Sill Torres

ID	Start	Title	Authors
B1-1	09:10	Cyber-Physical Security and Resilience for Offshore Wind Farms	Jennifer Mielniczek, Jennifer Mielniczek, Corinna Köpke, Kushal Srivastava, Egon Schröder
B1-2	09:30	Cyber-resilient Navigation in Coastal Waters	Roberto Galeazzi, Mogens Blanke, Dimitrios Dagdilelis, Morten C. Nissov, Rasmus H. Andersen and Josef Oehmen
B1-3	09:50	Design for Resilience: The Role of Integrated Safety and Security Assessment	Josef Oehmen, Nelson Carreras Guzman and Roberto Galeazzi
B1-4	10:10	Rebound Features of Offshore Wind Farm with Operation and Maintenance Service	Bartosz Skobiej, Arto Niemi, Nikolai Kulev and Frank Sill Torres

Session A2 - Autonomous systems

Session Chair David Heuskin

ID	Start	Title	Authors
A2-1	10:50	A Feasibility Analysis of Tether Localisation for Mobile Robots	Yasin Alhamwy, Simon Watson, Joaquin Carrasco, Glen Cooper and Kurt Geihs
A2-2	11:10	An Energy Consumption Model for Autonomous Underwater Vehicles in OMNeT++	Helge Parzyjeglá, Robert Hamann and Peter Danielis
A2-3	11:30	ESANAV: Enhanced Surrounding Awareness and Navigation for Autonomous Vessels	Michael Wilby, Patrick Talon, Juan Ignacio Bravo Pérez-Villar and Paulo Rosa
A2-S	11:50	Robotic Infrared Vision: Enabling operation in fog and low-light environments	Leonard Günzel

Session B2 - ELSA

Session Chair Carl Wrede

ID	Start	Title	Authors
B2-1	10:50	Enhanced Transparency: Improving Maritime Cyber Governance Resilience, Acceptability and the Postcolonial Moment – Towards a Culture-Sensitive Approach to Security Research in Maritime Contexts	Rory Hopcraft, Kemedi Moara-Nkwe, Kimberly Tam and Kevin Jones Bruno Arich-Gerz and Nicola Wendt
B2-2	11:10	Marine environmental ethics: an ecocentric renaissance?	Colin von Negenborn
B2-3	11:30	Responsible Technology Transfer: Market Introduction of Passive Scanning Systems (COSMICS)	Verena Nickel

Session A3 - Information Fusion/Extraction 1

Session Chair Edgardo Solano Carrillo

ID	Start	Title	Authors
A3-1	13:00	Comparison of detectability of ship wake components between C- and X-Band Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR)	Björn Tings, James Imber, Stefan Wiehle and Sven Jacobsen
A3-2	13:20	Deep Learning Based Oil Spill Detection Using Sentinel-1 SAR Data	Yi-Jie Yang and Suman Singha
A3-3	13:40	The COSMICS (Container Scanning by Muon-based Imaging using Cosmic rayS) project	Sarah Barnes, Maurice Stephan, Frank Sill Torres, Alexander Gabriel, Arto Niemi, Carl Wrede and Nicola Wendt

Session B3 - Sensors

Session Chair Sven Schröder

ID	Start	Title	Authors
B3-1	13:00	A Gated-Viewing instrument for maritime security and search and rescue applications	Enno Peters, Jendrik Schmidt, Susanne Wollgarten and Matthias Mischung
B3-2	13:20	Advanced acoustic imaging systems for underwater close-range volumetric navigation, object detection and identification	Michael Ehrhardt
B3-3	13:40	Monitoring offshore structures during project planning, installation and operation	Stefan Raimund

Session A4 - Cyber-Security 1

Session Chair Jannis Stoppe

ID	Start	Title	Authors
A4-1	14:20	A Cyber Security Test Environment for Bridge Systems	Christian Hemminghaus, Mari Schmidt and Jan Bauer
A4-2	14:40	Where are my containers?	Marc Asendorf, Hasanur Jaman Seam, Christian Maeder, Salva Daneshgadeh

A4-3	15:00	From an Informed Maritime Community to Cyber Resilient Ports	Çakmakçı and Bernhard J. Berger Salva Daneshgadeh Çakmakçı, Jil Tietjen, Bernhard J. Berger and Christian Maeder
------	-------	--	---

Session B4 - Communication

Session Chair Enno Peters

ID	Start	Title	Authors
B4-1	14:20	Security challenges in multi-modal communication	Karin Bernsmed, Per Håkon Meland, Ravi Borgaonkar, Guillaume Bour and Egil Wille
B4-2	14:40	Redesign of communication systems at the German maritime SAR service by using TETRA technology	Niklas Frings, Sylvia Bach and Frank Fiedrich
B4-3	15:00	Modeling Underwater Communication for Autonomous Underwater Vehicles in OMNeT++	Peter Danielis, Mostafa Assem Mohamed Ali and Helge Parzyjegl

Session A5 - Cyber-Security 2

Session Chair Malte Struck

ID	Start	Title	Authors
A5-1	15:40	Threat Modeling Knowledge for the Maritime Community	Bernhard J. Berger, Christian Maeder and Salva Daneshgadeh Çakmakçı
A5-2	16:00	A Review of Maritime Cyber Security Regulations	Aljoscha Windhorst and Jannis Stoppe
A5-3	16:20	IT Security Monitoring at a Port Terminal Operator	Jens Wettlaufer, Matthias Marx, Jens Lindemann and Hannes Federrath

Session B5 - Information Fusion/Extraction 2

Session Chair Edgardo Solano Carrillo

ID	Start	Title	Authors
B5-1	15:40	A Framework for Extended Multisensor Multitarget Tracking with Vessel Size Categorization	Aman Kumar and Jaya Shradha Fowdur
B5-2	16:00	Maritime Traffic Representation and Association with Graph and Machine Learning Techniques	Jaya Shradha Fowdur, Sandeep Kumar Singh, Juan C. Machuca and Daniel Arias Medina
B5-3	16:20	Enhancing the underwater vision to increase the safety of heavy underwater works by Intersensory learning – a use case in the European DeeperSense research project	Christian Illing and Tom Runge
B5-S	16:40	Single Page Applications – Modular situational awareness tools for data visualization	Tobias Höbbel